

ADVANCES IN GLOBAL BUSINESS RESEARCH

Vol. 4, No. 1
ISSN 1549 - 9332

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EXAMINATION OF THE CAUSES OF IT PROJECTS FAILURE WITHIN THE PUBLIC SECTOR: STATE OF QATAR

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ABSTRACT

Information technology (IT) project management is a crucial issue for organizations today due to the time, resources, and high budgets. This paper examines the causes of IT projects failure within the public sector in State of Qatar. The paper investigates the primary reasons causing IT projects to fail, delayed, and goes over budget. The paper attempts to determine what causes management fail to foresee project failure. This is achieved by surveying government branches and government owned Oil & Gas companies in an attempt to outline the primary reasons causing IT projects to fail. Analysis of the surveyed sample shows that lack of communications, constant change in projects requirements, lack of clarity in projects scope, lack of individual skills in project management, are the leading factors causing IT projects to fail in the Qatari public sector.

INTRODUCTION

Consensus among information technology managers and people involved in IT project suggests that IT project in the state of Qatar has a high tendency of failure in the public sector. This high rate of failure is creating waste of resources, and dissipation of public funds (Bryde, 2003). It is the objective of this paper to examine this phenomenon in an attempt to determine the causes leading to such high failure rate. IT projects in the public sector occurs primarily in government branches such as ministries and oil and gas companies owned by the state of Qatar. To understand the nature of the problem, a survey was developed and distributed to employees in the oil and gas companies such as Qatar Gas, RUS Gas, and Qatar Petroleum. The survey was an English-language and consistent of nine questions asking participants to choose the main reasons contributing to projects failure. Thus, wide array of government employees from different branches of the government are participating in determining why IT projects tends to fail. The oil and gas industry which is the largest public sector government represents an excellent testing ground for surveying the causes of IT projects failure. In addition, some key government ministries were chosen to provide a representation of typical government environment where IT projects take place. The object is to convert all the data obtained and run statistical analysis to determine if a pattern exists between IT projects failure in the oil and gas industry and other government branches. However, the main objective of this research paper is to determine the main causes contributing to the higher rate of IT projects failures. Better understanding of such causes will contribute significantly to the body of knowledge in the field of project-management, by sharing the lessons learned (Liebowitz, 1999). This is especially true in the case of the State of Qatar and the surrounding region, which enjoys similar economic and cultural characteristics, and where high economic development and mega projects are taking place. The results of this research paper will be shared with the participants in this study in an effort to create greater understanding of the nature of projects and the contributing factors causing IT projects to fail in hope to increase the likelihood of future projects successes. This paper will start by introducing the literature review, then the research methodology followed by statement of the problem, the research questions, data collection, data analysis, then findings and summary.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Information technology (IT) projects are vital to organizations in both public and the private sector. Extensive literature has been written on this subject examining the causes and the processes of project-management failures across all industries. However, little literature has been written on the subject examining the causes for projects failure in State of Qatar. Whittaker (1999) examined projects failure in Canada. In both public and the private sector and found that the three main reasons for IT projects failure are poor project planning, lack of management supports, and weak business case. Whittaker (1999) added that poor understanding of business needs actually leads to weak business case, which makes it harder to gain top management support for IT projects. Whittaker's research also found that running over budget wasn't as important to management as projects running overtime. Brennan, & Orwig, (2000) stated that many projects lacks good understanding of scope definition, project objectives, stakeholders taking interest in the project, information collection and gathering, distribution of information gathered, and information and management. What Brennan & Orwig referring to is the importance of collecting information to gain better understanding of the project

scope, and building business case for project initiation, that reflects business needs. Cicmil, (1997) argued that organization lack good understanding of the requirements of projects management, and project management. Cicmil clearly indicates that such lack of understanding among staff in modern organizations may lead to high rate of project failure. Elonen & Arto, (2003) however, argued that project failures are caused by lack of resources allocated between different projects within the organization. While Engwall & Jerbrant, (2003) perceived that the focus of projects management should be on defining organizational objectives, which leads to a better understanding of project objectives. This confirmed Dooley, (2000) argument that proper understanding of project objectives is a key factor in determining projects success. Khalfan, and Alshawaf (2003) assert that social and cultural factors are key ingredients of a successful implementation of IT projects in the Gulf states, which includes countries like Qatar, Kuwait, Saudi Arabia, UAE, Oman, and Bahrain. Although cultural values, plays a role in determining the interactions and the outcome of a project, yet the characteristics and principles of project management remains the same worldwide, Kerzner, (2004), Ghattas and Mckee (2001). Most project managers in the oil and gas industry in Qatar and surrounding region are either Western educated or certified managers by Western standard institutions. Khalfan and Alshawaf (2003) do emphasize that point. Outsourcing for IS/IT will continue to increase in these countries in the coming years making it one of the most important regions for IT project, Powl & Skitmore (2005). Finally, keeping track of projects performance and projects successes or failures is rare phenomena in Qatar and the surrounding region. Only mega projects are recorded in terms of completion time. In many instances, actual cost for such large projects is not properly recorded or intentionally inflated. This is caused by lack of transparency or corruption. Record keeping regarding government spending on various projects will most definitely help in better understanding the actual causes for projects failure and IS/IT projects, Marquez & Herguedas (2004).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The main purpose of this section is to present the specific methodology procedures employed in testing the IT people perceptions. This section consists of several main items. The first item will deal with statement of problem then the objectives of the study. The research questions will be developed in the third section. The fourth and fifth sections will be appropriated to the scope of the study and the study's limitations. The sample and the questionnaire, which is considered to be the main tool for gathering data, will be discussed in the last section.

Statement of problem

IT projects in the state of Qatar is experiencing higher rate of failure. Projects are either terminated before deadline, exceed deadlines, or go way beyond allocated budgets. Therefore, a study needed to be conducted to determine the causes contributing to failure of IT projects by examining key content contributing factors that are known to be on long the main reasons for projects failure

Objectives of the study

The objective of this study is to determine what specific factors causing IT project to fail in the public sector in State of Qatar. Revealing the core causes for project failure will expand knowledge on the nature of projects and will help better understand what is contributing to such high rate of failure in the public sector in an effort to create awareness among people involved in IT projects within the public sector. Additionally, exposing employees involved in public IT projects to the problems of other government institutions facing in similar projects, in hope to reduce future projects failure by creating greater awareness of the key contributing factors to IT projects failure.

Research Questions

This study attempts to answer the following questions;

1. Is poor understanding of project scope and requirements leads to IT projects failure?
2. Is time and resources that is required to accomplish assigned projects are not properly allocated?
3. Is lack of commitment and communications causing IT projects to fail?
4. Is changing requirements and lack of experience in project management skills causing IT projects to fail?

Scope of the study

This study examines only IT projects within the public sector in the state of Qatar. The scope of the study does not go beyond the public sector and does not examine all government branches. However, key government institutions including oil and gas companies are surveyed and where IT projects are known to take place frequently and employees are known to participate regularly in IT projects. The scope for this project is limited to determining the key factors that cause public IT projects to go beyond budgets and overtime.

Value of Study

The study provides unique contribution to the body of knowledge in project management in regards to this part of the world. Furthermore, the paper provides some indications to better understand the business environment and cultural drives that largely contribute to projects successes and failure in State of Qatar and the surrounding region.

Data Collection

A survey was developed that constitutes nine questions regarding the main cases of IT projects failure in the public sector. All variables are measured with questionnaire data. Most of the items used here have been borrowed partly or wholly from other research instruments which have demonstrated reliability and validity. These items were used in the questionnaire in order to give this study a comparative base with other previous research. Items and scales were tested through a pilot study carried out in two ways: Firstly, the researchers contacted two associate professors and two assistant professors in management area. Secondly, the questionnaire was pilot tested among sixteen employees involved in IT project in one government institution and one main Oil and Gas Company (eight employees from each). The sample for pilot study was obtained in the same manner as for the main study. They were asked to complete the questionnaire according to the instructions and then to carefully review all the items from a critical perspective to seek out problems such as ambiguity or redundancy. The results of the pre-test suggested that there was little need for version. In additions, none of the respondents involved with the pre-test indicted any degree of difficulty in interpreting the questions as presented. Feedback from these two government institutions was taken into consideration and helped to shape the final draft of the survey. Subsequently, a website was created that includes all nine questions of the survey. An e-mail was sent to all employees in the oil and gas companies with a link to the survey to make the process of participating in the study fast and easy. Participants are able to click the corresponding answer to each question why they click of their mouse. Furthermore, semi structured interviews were conducted with managers in government branches including oil and gas companies, who are involved regularly in IT projects. Their feed back was highly valuable to the construction of the survey. The non-oil and gas government institutions participated in this study by filling out a paper copy of the survey. This is because employees of government institutions in Qatar tend to hesitate in participating in online surveys. Unlike employees in the oil and gas sector, where the nature of their job requires them to be heavily involved in electronic communications, this is also due to the size of their organizations. While employees in traditional government institutions enjoys closer contacts among themselves and physically located within the same building, which makes the process of distributing and collecting paper surveys much easier and more effective. The data collected from both the paper survey and the electronic survey was entered into the SPSS statistical data analysis software to run statistical analysis for the purpose of this study. The total survey collected both electronically and paper surveys mounted to 102 however, only 98 surveys were usable. 4 surveys were missing values in more than half of the questions asked and some of the answers were unclear therefore, it was decided to leave them out and not to include them in the analysis.

ANALYSIS

Descriptive Statistics

All 98 surveys have 0 missing values. That means that all field in the 98 surveys we filled and not one missed. The first set of analysis to run is the frequency analysis to determine patterns of occurrence in the answers provided. The survey asks participants to rate the main reasons for project's failure by using five points scale, ranging from strongly agree to strongly disagree. Variable 1 of the questionnaire deals with the defining of the project scope. Table 1 showing, that a substantial majority of replies (77.6%) rated this factor as a reason for IT projects failure which reflects a problem in projects scope definition. Turning to question two of the survey, which asks whether project requirements are not clearly defined, the same general pattern emerges. It is observed that (74.5%) of the respondents agree or strongly agreeing with the statement reflecting a high percentage relating to unclear defined project requirements as a reason for IT projects failure. Variable 3 of the survey asks participants whether they think IT projects they took part of were unrealistic. Only (24.5%) thinks that the IT projects were unrealistic, however (59.2%) of participants believe that projects were realistic. Perhaps this is the most striking result shown in Table 1. Variable 4 of the survey asks whether not enough time was allocated to projects, which contributed to project failure. (61.2.8%) Of the replies believed that this could be one of the contributing factors to IT projects failure. Only (17.3%) thinks that there was enough time allocated to the projects. Variable 5 of the survey asks whether not enough resources were allocated to projects. Only (39.8%) of participants agree or strongly agreeing with the statement, whereas (45.9%) of the replies reported that this issue was not a reason for the IT projects failure. Variable 6 of the survey asks whether there is lack of commitment for the project by the people involved, (61.2%) agree or strongly agree that there is a lack of commitment by people involved in projects. Only (31.6%) of the respondents indicted that lack of commitment did not contribute to the failure of the IT projects in Qatari public sector. Table 1 also show that changing deliverables and requirements were seen as the most frequent reason for the project failure, the considerable majority of replies (81.6%) agree or strongly agree with the statement, while only (5.1%) considered this factor as not reason for the failure of the IT projects. Variable 8 of the survey asks whether lack of communications is contributing to project failure. As with the previous factor, respondents agree or strongly agree that the item used to measure this factor was influential cause of IT projects failure (81.6%), while only (1%) strongly disagree with the statement. Variable 9 of the survey asks whether lack of experience by people involved in projects is contributing to project failure. (70.4%) of the respondents agreeing or strongly agree with the statement, while only (12.2%) strongly disagree. Therefore, it seems clear that the majority of the responses shown in Table 1 indicate that lack of experience by people involved in projects is a leading factor in IT projects' failure.

Correlation analysis

Although frequencies analysis was perform, it is worthwhile looking at correlation coefficients between these variables to investigate their relationships and how they related to each other.

Table 1
Factors Affecting IT project's Failure

Factors	Strongly agree		Agree		Uncertain		Disagree		Strongly disagree	
	Freq	Per	Freq	Per	Freq	Per	Freq	Per	Freq	Per
Project scope is not well defined	49	50.00	27	27.6	9	9.2	8	8.2	5	5.1
Project requirements are not clearly defined	59	60.2	14	14.3	6	6.1	5	5.1	14	14.3
Project is not realistic	16	16.3	8	8.2	16	16.3	18	18.4	40	40.8
Not enough time allocated	38	38.8	22	22.4	21	21.4	12	12.2	5	5.1
Not enough resources allocated	25	25.5	14	14.3	14	14.3	12	12.2	33	33.7
Lack of commitment by people involved	50	51.0	10	10.2	7	7.1	2	2.00	29	29.6
Changing deliverables and requirements	70	71.4	10	10.2	13	13.2	2	2.00	3	3.1
Lack of communications	66	67.3	14	14.3	15	15.3	2	2.00	1	1.00
Lack of experience by people involved in the project	56	57.1	13	13.3	14	14.3	3	3.1	12	12.2

Left column represent Frequencies. Right column represent Percentages.

Table 2
Correlation Matrix among Variables for the Responses of People Involved in IT Projects in Qatari Public Sector

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1. Project scope is not well defined	1								
2. Project requirements are not clearly defined	.427(**)	1							
3. Project is not realistic	.243(*)	.322(**)	1						
4 Not enough time allocated.	.107	.348(**)	.292(**)	1					
5. Not enough resources allocated	.282(**)	.242(*)	.280(**)	.468(**)	1				
6. Lack of commitment by people involved	.265(**)	.291(**)	.300(**)	.371(**)	.662(**)	1			
7. Changing deliverables and requirements	.165	.143	.014	.274(**)	.349(**)	.438(**)	1		
8 Lack of communications.	.263(**)	.432(**)	.208(*)	.269(**)	.419(**)	.628(**)	.527(**)	1	
9. Lack of experience by people involved in the project	.119	.210(*)	.119	.233(*)	.326(**)	.434(**)	.432(**)	.533(**)	1

*p <.05. **p <.01.

Pearson's correlation test has revealed that there is a strong correlation between variable's one and two as a correlation coefficient $r = .427$ and $p < 0.01$, this indicates that project scope and project requirements are significantly contributing to project failure. Furthermore, there is a significant correlation between requirements being not clearly defined (variable 1) and project being not unrealistic (variable 3) as $r = .322$ and $p < 0.01$. Another significant correlation exists between (variable 4) and (variable 3) as $r = .292$ and $p < 0.01$, which is the relationship between projects being enough realistic and not enough time allocated to complete the projects. This indicates that when projects are not realistic, they contribute significantly to the time projects take to complete. The two factors are contradicting factors to produce failure as well. There is a positive correlation exists between (variable 5) and (variable 1), which is project scope being not well defined and the resources allocated to the project as $r = .282$ and $p < 0.01$, this indicates that when project scope is not well defined it is highly related to the resources associated with the project. This also point out that when project scope is miss defined, resources are not properly allocated to the project. The correlation between (variable 2) and variable 5) $r = .242$ and $p < 0.05$, which indicates that there is a strong relationship between project requirements are not clearly defined, and not enough recourses allocated to projects. The same relationship exist between (variable 5) and (variable 3) resources allocation and projects not being realistic as $r = .280$ and $p < 0.01$. Also, not enough resource allocation is impacting the time projects take as the relationship between (variables 5) and (variable 4) $r = .468$ and $p < 0.01$. Furthermore, the lack of commitment by people involved in projects is causing projects to fail as the correlation between variable nine and several other variables are as follows. Variable six and variable one is correlated at $r = .265$ and $p < 0.01$, which indicated that when project scope is not well defined, higher lack of commitment occurs by the people involved in projects. The lack of commitment also occur when project requirements are not clearly defined, as the relationship between (variables 6) and (variable 2) at $r = .291$ and $p < 0.01$. Lack of commitment by projects participants is reduces when the project is not being realistic as the relationship between (variable 6) and (variable 3) at $r = .300$ and $p < 0.01$. Lack of commitment to projects occurs also when not enough time is allocated as the relationship between (variables 6) and (variable 4) at $r = .371$ and $p < 0.01$. Not enough recourse allocation is also reducing the commitment to projects by participants as the relationship between (variables 6) and (variable 5) at $r = .662$ and $p < 0.01$.

In addition, the change in deliverables and projects requirements is significantly impacting several variables as follows. Change in deliverables and project requirements is impacting project time allocation as the relationship between (variables 7) and (variable 4) at $r = .274$ and $p < 0.01$. Not enough resources allocated to project also impacting changing deliverables and project requirements as the relationship between (variables 7) and (variable 5) at $r = .349$. Change in deliverables and project requirements is significantly impacting the level of commitment by project participants as the relationship between (variables 7) and (variable 6) shows $r = .438$ and $p < 0.01$. Correlation analysis also shows that a strong relationship exists between lack of communications and project scope not being well defined as $r = .263$ and $p < 0.01$, in (variable 8) and (variable 1). This relationship seems to be natural and highly correlated in project management. There is a high impact of luck of communications on project requirements being not clearly defined as the relationship between (variable 8) and (variable 2) at $r = .432$ and $p < 0.01$. Lack of communications is causing not enough time to be allocated to projects as the relationship between (variable 8) and (variable 4) is $r = .269$ and $p < 0.01$. Furthermore, lack of communications is also closing insufficient resources to be allocated to projects as a relationship between (variables 8) and (variable 5) at $r = .419$ and $p < 0.01$. Lack of communications is also causing lack of commitment by people involved in projects as the relationship between (variables 8) and (variable 6) $r = .628$ and $p < 0.01$, and the lack of communications is impacting the changing deliverables and project requirements as a relationship between (variables 8) and (variable 7) at $r = .527$ and $p < 0.01$. Additionally, lack of experiences of IT projects personal is causing insufficient resources to be allocated to projects, which is also contributing to projects failures as the relationship between (variables 9) and (variable 5) is $r = .326$ and $p < 0.01$. Lack of experience of the people involved in IT projects is also causing lack of commitment by people involved in these projects. This is shown in the relationship between (variables 9) and (variable 6) is $r = .434$ and $p < 0.01$, and lack of experience by the people involved in projects is causing a continuous change in project deliverables and project requirements. This is shown in the relationship between (variables 9) and (variable 7) as $r = .432$ and $p < 0.01$. The relationship between variables nine and variable eight shows that lack of experience by project participants is causing the lack of communications. This is verified in the relationship as $r = .533$ and $p < 0.01$.

DISCUSSION

The results of the study shows that strong lack of communications exist between the people involved in IT projects is significantly contributing to projects failure. Continuous change in project requirements by adding and dropping deliverables throughout the project is sought to be attributed to the high rate of project failures, which confirms Loo's (2003) and Kerzner's (2004) findings. The analysis further shows that lack of clarity in project's objectives strongly contributes to IT projects failure. This also corresponds with Kerzner (2004) findings and supports Bryde's (2003) findings. Additionally, new IT projects initiation tends to have poor scope, which is causing projects to be extended way beyond the time frame set for the project and way beyond allocated budgets. Moreover, analysis of the population sampled further shows that individuals involved in IT projects in State of Qatar lacks essential project management skills, which is significantly plays a part in projects failures. This finding corresponds with Cicmil (1997). Better preparation of people involved in IT project in project management skills may contribute significantly to improving communications and project success. Analysis of the data collected indicates that high-level management involved in public projects need to recognizing the importance of project scope and clear project requirements. Furthermore, public sector organizations need to develop better project management skills, policies procedures, training, improving the individual capabilities of people involved in project, and by conducting better project estimation. The findings of this research also affirm previous research findings by Khalfan and Alshawaf (2003), both findings asserts that essential skills such as general project management, legal understanding, project monitoring and control can significantly contribute to projects success. This paper is limited to the investigation of the issues involved in projects failure within the public sector in the State of Qatar. Moreover it is largely comprised of oil and gas industry and government organizations that are highly involved in project initiation, monitoring and project control. The scope of this paper does not include the private sector and does not attempt to do so. Further comparative research should be conducted to determine whether projects in the public sector in Qatar fail for the same reasons as in other parts of the world. Understanding whether the public sector in Qatar enjoys unique characteristics that separate it from other public sectors in other countries will be beneficial to the general project management body of knowledge.

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